

TABLE I - PHYSICAL DATA OF THE CARBAZOLES (1)*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p.** °C
1a	H	H	H	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	69	238-40 ^a
1b	Br	H	Br	Br	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₃	62	206-08 ^a
1c	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄	58	234-36 ^b
1d	NO ₂	H	H	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	66	230-32 ^a
1e	H	NO ₂	H	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	63	238-40 ^b
1f	H	H	NO ₂	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	65	238-40 ^a
1g	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	67	238-40 ^a
1h	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	64	98-100 ^a
1i	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	69	238-40 ^a
1j	Br	H	Br	Br	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr	73	228-30 ^b
1k	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄	61	228-30 ^a
1l	H	H	H	H	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	68	220-22 ^b

*All compounds showed satisfactory analytical results for C, H and N.
**Solvents for crystallisation: ^aMeOH, ^bMe₂CO, ^cC₆H₆.

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Scheme 1

Thiocarbazine acids. Part-III. Synthesis of 1,2,4-Triazole Derivatives

MADHUKAR S. CHANDE* and ANIL V. KARNIK

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, 15 Madame Cama Road, Bombay-400 032

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IN continuation of our studies on the chemistry of carbon oxysulphide¹, we now report the reaction of benzyl-β-phenyl thiocarbazine (1)² with alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates and isocyanates.

Compound 1 on treatment with alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates (Scheme 1), afforded the corresponding 1-phenyl-4-alkyl/aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazolidin-3-ones (2; Table I). One of the compounds, viz. 1,4-diphenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazolidin-3-one (2a; R=Ph) showed ir band (nujol) at 1730 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Its pmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆) showed signals at δ 5.8 (1H, s, NH) and 7.3-8.0 (10H, m, ArH).

TABLE I - PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2-4

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	Yield %	M p, °C	ν _{C=O} , cm ⁻¹
2a	Phenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO	65	217	1730
2b	p-Tolyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO	63	231	1725
2c	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ SOCl	67	251	1735
2d	p-Anisyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO ₂	68	220	1715
2e	Methyl	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ SO	62	235	1705
3a	Phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	91	147	-
3b	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	92	168	-
3c	1-Naphthyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	91	175	-
3d	Cyclohexyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₂ S	91	165	-
4a	Phenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	81	166	1780 1710 1782
4b	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	84	206	1720 1785
4c	1-Naphthyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	79	225	1710 1790
4d	Cyclohexyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	76	215	1715

NOTES

Benzyl- β -phenylthiocarbazine (1) on treatment with alkyl/aryl isocyanates in benzene gave the corresponding benzyl β -alkyl/aryl carbamylthiocarbazine (3^a; Table 1). When refluxed in alkaline medium, compound 3 afforded the corresponding 1-phenyl-4-alkyl/aryl-1,2,4-triazolidin-3,5-diones (4; Table 1). One of these, viz. 1,4-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazolidin-3,5-dione (4_a; R=Ph) showed ir band at 1780 and 1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Its pmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆) showed peaks at δ 7.0–7.8 (10H, m, ArH) and 5.7 (1H, s, NH).

The antimicrobial activities of compounds 2 and 4 were tested against *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* using plate-diffusion method⁴. Compounds 2 were found to be very active against *E. coli* and moderately active against *B. subtilis*, and 4 were found to be moderately active against *E. coli*.

Experimental

Benzyl- β -phenyl thiocarbazine (1): Through a solution of phenyl hydrazine (0.05 mol) and triethylamine (0.05 mol) in dry methanol (30 ml), a stream of dry carbon oxysulphide was passed for about 20 min and then benzyl chloride (0.05 mol) was added to it. The passing of carbon oxysulphide was continued for 2.5 h. The contents were then poured on crushed ice and triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 171°.

1-Phenyl-4-substituted-5-thio-1,2,4-triazolidin-3-ones (2): A mixture of 1 (0.02 mol), alkyl/aryl-isothiocyanate (0.02 mol) and aqueous alcoholic sodium hydroxide (10%; 30 ml) was refluxed for 90 min. The contents were then poured in cold water, acidified with dilute HCl, and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol.

Benzyl- β -substituted-carbamyl thiocarbazine (3): A mixture of 1 (0.02 mol) and alkyl/arylisocyanate (0.02 mol) was refluxed in benzene for 30 min. After removing benzene, the resulting solid was crystallised.

1-Phenyl-4-substituted-1,2,4-triazolidin-3,4-diones (4): Compound 3 (0.02 mol) was refluxed in aqueous sodium hydroxide for 30 min. The contents were then poured into crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol.

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Synthesis and Application of some New Quinolinofurandione Derivatives as Bactericides

AMAL S. YANNI* and ZARIF H. KHALIL

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt

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SEVERAL heterocyclic quinones possess properties as dyes¹, catalysts² and drugs³, and this led to a renewed attention to their synthesis from 6,7-dichloroquinoline-5,8-quinone.

Results and Discussion

Naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-dione is obtained from 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone by condensing 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with an active methylene group compound in ethanol and in presence of tributylamine⁴. It is therefore expected that 6,7-dichloroquinoline-5,8-quinone can react similarly with active methylene group compounds such as acetylacetone, ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl cyanoacetate, and diethyl malonate to give 6-disubstituted-methyl-7-chloroquinoline-5,8-dione (1), and the cyclisation of 1 in ethanol and in presence of tributylamine

- 1a; R=CH₃, R₁=COCH₃ 2a; R=CH₃, R₁=COCH₃
1b; R=CH₃, R₁=COOC₂H₅ 2b; R=CH₃, R₁=COOC₂H₅
1c; R=OC₂H₅, R₁=CN 2c; R=OC₂H₅, R₁=CN
1d; R=OC₂H₅, R₁COOC₂H₅ 2d; R=OC₂H₅, R₁=COOC₂H₅

yield 2. In another route, compounds 2 could be prepared in one step by condensing 6,7-dichloro-